

Oxidation of Methionine by Sodium *N*-Bromobenzene-sulphonamide in Aqueous Solution. A Kinetic and Mechanistic Study

S. ANANDA, K. S. RANGAPPA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Mysore, Manasagangotri, Mysore-570 006

Manuscript received 1 July 1985, revised 17 February 1986, accepted 2 April 1986

Kinetics of oxidation of DL-methionine (Mt) in the presence of HCl, HClO₄, H₂SO₄ and NaOH by sodium *N*-bromobenzenesulphonamide (BAB) have been investigated at 40° (and 30° in alkaline medium). The rate law is identical in the three acids,

$$-\frac{d[\text{BAB}]}{dt} = k[\text{BAB}][\text{H}^+]^2$$

In alkaline medium, the rate law shows a first order dependence each on [BAB] and [OH⁻]. Effect of halide (Cl⁻ or Br⁻) ion was studied. Addition of the reaction product, benzenesulphonamide retards the rate. Variation of ionic strength has no effect on the rate. The solvent isotope effect was studied using D₂O. Activation parameters have also been determined. Methioninesulphone is identified as the reaction product. Mechanisms proposed and the derived rate laws are in agreement with the observed kinetics.

RECENTLY, bromamine-B (sodium *N*-bromobenzene-sulphonamide, C₆H₅SO₂NBrNa.1.5H₂O, hereinafter abbreviated as BAB) has been introduced¹ as an oxidimetric reagent in aqueous medium. A review of literature shows that although the reactions of aromatic sulphonyl chloramines have been extensively investigated, there is meagre information on the reaction of corresponding bromamines. Oxidation of α-amino acids² and dimethyl sulphoxide³ by BAB has been kinetically studied. As a part of our board programme on the mechanistic aspects of oxidation of substrates by aromatic bromamines, we report the kinetics of oxidation of methionine by the title reagent in acid and alkaline media.

The oxidation of amino acids is of utmost importance, both from chemical point of view and from its bearing on the mechanism of amino acid metabolism. There are very few reports on the kinetics of oxidation of amino acids by halogen compounds. Kumar *et al.*⁴ have studied the mechanism of oxidation of some amino acids by alkaline CAT. Wright⁵ reported oxidation of amino acids by OCl⁻ ion and showed that chlorination occurred in acid medium while alkalinity increased the tendency towards oxidation of the compounds.

Methionine (Mt) is an optically active essential sulphur-containing amino acid, important in biological transmethylation processes. It is used in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, nutrition and biochemical studies and as a food and feed supplement. Methionine has been oxidised to the sulphoxide by iodine⁶, bromine⁷, KBrO₃⁸ and ICl⁹, while NaClO₂⁹,

H₂O₂¹⁰ and bromate mixture⁷ convert it into the sulphone. Analytical methods have been devised for the estimation of this amino acid using aromatic *N*-haloamines¹¹. However, except for the work of Gensch and Higuchi⁶ and Young and Hsieh¹², no kinetic data are available for the oxidation of Mt with any of the reagents. A nearer example is the study of Mann-Pope reaction, *i.e.* conversion of sulphides with *N*-haloamines in buffered water-ethanol mixtures, by Ruff and Kucsman¹³. The present studies report for the first time the mechanism of oxidation of a sulphur-containing amino acid with bromamine-B.

Experimental

Bromamine-B was prepared by the reported procedure¹. The purity of BAB was checked iodometrically through an assay of its active bromine content and was further characterised by its ¹³C FT-nmr spectrum obtained on a Bruker WH 270 MHz spectrometer with D₂O as solvent, TMS as the external standard, (ppm relative to TMS) at 143.38 (C-1, carbon attached to S atom): 134.30 (C-4, *para* to the hetero atom) 131.26 (C-2,6) and 129.31 (C-3,5).

An aqueous solution of BAB was standardised iodometrically and preserved in brown bottles to prevent its photochemical deterioration. Chromatographically pure DL-methionine (Merck) was further assayed by the perchloric acid method¹⁴ and its aqueous solution was prepared. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade. The ionic strength of the

system was kept at a high value by using a concentrated solution of sodium perchlorate. Heavy-water (D₂O, 99.2%) employed for solvent isotope studies was supplied by the Bhabha Atomic Research Center (Trombay).

Stoichiometry: Varying ratios of BAB to amino acid in the presence of HClO₄, HCl, H₂SO₄ and NaOH were equilibrated at 40° for acids (and at 3° in alkali) for 24 h. The unreacted BAB in the reaction mixtures was determined by iodometric titration. The analysis showed that one mole of methionine reacted with two moles of BAB. The observed reaction stoichiometry is represented as

where, Ar is C₆H₅.

Product analysis: Benzenesulphonamide (ArSO₂-NH₂) was detected by paper chromatography. Benzyl alcohol saturated with water was used as the solvent with 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ethanol as spray reagent (R_f=0.905). The identification of methioninesulphone was also made through paper chromatography by employing n-butanol-glacial acetic acid-water (4:1:5, v/v) as solvent and 0.2% solution of ninhydrin in butanol-water-acetic acid (95:4:0.5, v/v) as spray reagent (R_f=0.17). Kinetic procedure followed was as reported in the earlier communications^{2,3}.

Results

The kinetics of oxidation of methionine by BAB were investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants, in acid and alkaline media.

Acid medium:

At constant [H⁺], with the substrate in stoichiometric excess, plots of log [BAB] vs time were linear (r > 0.998 0), indicating a first order dependence of rate on [oxidant] (Table 1). Values of the pseudo-first order rate constants, k', are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF METHIONINE BY BAB IN ACID MEDIA AT 40°

[HClO₄] = [HCl] = 0.07 M, [Mt] = 0.01 M, μ = 0.5 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.035 M

[BAB] ₀ × 10 ³ M	k', × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		
	HClO ₄	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄
3.0	3.76	13.92	2.06
4.0	3.80	14.08	2.12
5.0	3.98	14.13	2.19
6.0	3.96	14.21	2.24
7.0	4.08	14.34	2.31
8.0	4.11	14.41	2.39
Average	3.94 ± 0.14	14.17 ± 0.18	2.21 ± 0.12

The values of k' were unaffected with increase in [Mt]₀, indicating that the rate was independent of [amino acid] (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING [Mt] ON RATE OF REACTION AT 40°

[HClO₄] = [HCl] = 0.07 M, [BAB] = 0.005 M, μ = 0.5 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.035 M

[Mt] ₀ × 10 ³ M	k', × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		
	HClO ₄	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄
1.0	3.96	14.13	2.19
1.5	3.74	14.08	2.16
2.0	3.67	13.91	2.23
2.5	3.13	13.86	2.18
3.0	2.87	13.74	2.20
Average	3.47 ± 0.45	13.94 ± 0.16	2.19 ± 0.02

The rate increased with increase in [H⁺] (Table 3). Plots of log k' vs log [H⁺] were linear in all the three acid media with a slope of two (r > 0.999 0). This is also confirmed by plotting k' vs [H⁺]² when the straight line obtained passes through the origin.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF [H⁺] ON RATE OF REACTION AT 40°

[BAB]₀ = 0.005 M, [Mt]₀ = 0.01 M, μ = 0.5 M

[H ⁺] × 10 ³ M	k', × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		
	HClO ₄	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄
4.0	—	5.57	0.71
5.0	2.20	8.89	—
6.0	3.02	12.9	—
7.0	4.19	17.5	2.19
8.0	5.42	22.2	—
9.0	7.82	28.0	—
10.0	8.98	—	4.27
14.0	—	—	8.42
16.0	—	—	10.99

The rate increased with addition of [Cl⁻] or [Br⁻] (Table 4). Plots of log k' vs log [halide] are straight lines with slopes less than unity (r > 0.988) in all three acid media, indicating a fractional order dependence on [Cl⁻] (order = 0.5–0.6) and [Br⁻] (order = 0.3–0.4).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF HALIDE ION ON RATE OF REACTION AT 40°

[BAB]₀ = 0.005 M, [Mt]₀ = 0.01 M, μ = 0.5 M, [HClO₄] = [HCl] = 0.07 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.035 M

[Cl ⁻] M [Br ⁻] × 10 ³ M	k', × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		
	HClO ₄	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄
0.00 (0.0)	3.79 (3.79)	— (13.90)	2.19 (2.19)
0.02 (2.0)	4.38 (5.34)	— (18.20)	2.90 (2.81)
0.04 (5.0)	5.97 (6.86)	— (20.16)	4.06 (3.76)
0.06 (10.0)	7.68 (9.95)	— (26.14)	5.02 (5.36)
0.07	—	13.90	—
0.08	10.00	16.05	5.81
0.09	—	17.50	—
0.12	—	19.20	—

Values in parenthesis refer to Br⁻.

Presence of ClO_4^- and SO_4^{2-} ions had no effect on the rate. This was confirmed by further addition of NaClO_4 and Na_2SO_4 to the reaction mixture.

Variation of ionic strength of the medium (0.08–0.65 M) or addition of the reaction product, benzenesulphonamide (upto 0.008 M) had no significant effect on the rate.

The reaction was also studied in aqueous methanol of varying composition. An increase in methanol content (0.30%) increases the rate of reaction. A plot of $\log k'$ vs $1/D$, where D is the dielectric constant of the medium, gave a straight line with a positive slope ($r > 0.9872$).

Kinetic studies were carried out in D_2O containing HClO_4 and $k'_{\text{D}_2\text{O}}$ was found to be $8.06 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ while the corresponding $k'_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ was $3.96 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ leading to the normal solvent isotope effect, $k'_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/k'_{\text{D}_2\text{O}}=0.49$.

The reaction was studied at different temperatures (30–45°). From the straight line plot of $\log k'$ vs $1/T$ ($r=0.9966$) for HClO_4 , $r=0.9999$ for HCl and $r=0.9945$ for H_2SO_4 , activation parameters were computed (Table 5).

TABLE 5—KINETIC AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF METHIONINE BY BAB IN ACIDIC AND ALKALINE MEDIA

	HClO_4	HCl	H_2SO_4	NaOH
$\log A$	10.1	12.7	10.0	9.0
$\Delta H^\ddagger \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$	64.8	73.0	65.4	53.7
$\Delta S^\ddagger \text{ JK mol}^{-1}$	-94.9	-65.7	-106.0	-121.9
$\Delta G^\ddagger \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$	94.2	93.4	98.8	90.9

Addition of reaction mixture to aqueous acrylamide solution did not initiate polymerisation, showing the absence of free radical species.

Alkaline medium :

At constant NaOH and substrate concentrations, the reaction showed a first order dependence on $[\text{BAB}]_0$ ($r > 0.9970$; Table 6). The values of k' were unaffected with increase in $[\text{Mt}]$, indicating that the rate was independent of [amino acid]. Values of k' increased with increase in $[\text{NaOH}]$ and a plot of $\log k'$ vs $\log [\text{NaOH}]$ was linear with a slope of unity ($r=0.9976$), indicating a first order dependence of rate on hydroxide ion concentration (Table 7). Here the reactive $(\text{OH}^-)_R$ was determined by the relation, $(\text{OH}^-)_R = (\text{OH}^-)_T - (\text{OH}^-)_{\text{Mt}}$, where $(\text{OH}^-)_T$ is the total concentration and $(\text{OH}^-)_{\text{Mt}}$ the hydroxyl ion concentration neutralised by the amino acid.

Addition of the reaction product, benzenesulphonamide (ArSO_2NH_2) retards the reaction rate, indicating that it is involved in an equilibrium (Table 7). A plot of $\log k'$ vs $\log [\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2]$ gave a straight line ($r=0.9886$) with a slope of -0.56 .

Addition of chloride to the reaction mixture and variation of ionic strength had no effect on the rate.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF $[\text{BAB}]_0$, $[\text{Mt}]_0$, ON RATE OF REACTION AT 30°

$[\text{NaOH}]_R = 0.01 M$, $\mu = 0.50 M$	$[\text{Mt}]_0$ $\times 10^3 M$	k' $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
	3.00	20.70
	4.00	20.30
	5.00	19.70
	6.00	19.50
	7.00	19.12
	8.00	18.96
	5.00	19.46
	5.00	19.78
	5.00	19.92
	5.00	19.96
	5.00	20.04
	5.00	20.15

TABLE 7—EFFECT OF VARYING $(\text{OH}^-)_R$ AND $[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2]$ ON RATE OF REACTION AT 30°

$[\text{BAB}]_0 = 0.005 M$, $(\text{OH}^-)_R$ $\times 10^3 M$	k' $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2] \times 10^3$ at $[\text{NaOH}]_R = 0.01 M$	k' $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
2.50	4.13	1.0	15.10
5.00	8.10	2.0	11.52
6.25	10.40	3.0	9.07
7.50	12.43	4.0	7.45
10.00	19.70	5.0	6.14
12.50	23.10	6.0	5.54
15.00	30.00	—	—

An increase in methanol content (0–30%) increases the rate of reaction. A plot of $\log k'$ vs $1/D$ gave a straight line ($r=0.9970$) with a positive slope.

Solvent isotope studies were made in D_2O medium. It was found that $k'_{\text{D}_2\text{O}} = 1.93 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, while $k'_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 1.97 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the solvent isotope effect $k'_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/k'_{\text{D}_2\text{O}} = 1.02$.

Discussion

It is interesting to note that, oxidation of methionine by BAB in acid and alkaline media obeys zero order kinetics in $[\text{Mt}]_0$, indicating that the substrate is oxidised in a fast step. The results in acid media are similar to those obtained for the oxidation of dimethyl sulphoxide⁸ by this bromamine, but the mechanism is different in alkaline medium for these substrates.

Acid medium :

Bromamine-B ($\text{ArSO}_2\text{NBrNa}$) is analogous to CAT^{15} and behaves like a strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions. It may be assumed that similar equilibria exist in acid solutions,

Dibromamine-B ($\text{ArSO}_2\text{NBr}_2$) and the free acid hydrolyse to give hypobromous acid (HOBr),

The possible oxidising species in acidified BAB solutions are therefore ArSO_2NBr , $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NBr}_2$, HOBr and Br_2 . The probability of the dibromo compound as the reactive species can be ruled out, as the rate follows a strict first order dependence on [BAB]. Since the added benzenesulphonamide did not retard the reaction, it may be assumed that HOBr is not primarily involved in the rate determining step. Detailed calculations of Hardy and Johnston¹⁶ have shown that the free acid is present in higher concentrations in acid media and it is the most likely oxidising species to be involved in the reaction sequence.

Formation of species of the type $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2^+\text{Cl}^-$ has been reported¹⁷ with CAT and the protonation constant for the reaction,

is found to be 1.02×10^3 at 25° .

The rate dependence on $[\text{H}^+]^2$ and [BAB] indicates a protonation step involving the oxidant, since the rate is independent of $[\text{Mt}]_0$. Scheme 1 accounts for the observed kinetics.

Scheme 1

Assuming steady state for $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Br}^+$, Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (9), in the form,

$$-\frac{d[\text{BAB}]}{dt} = k[\text{BAB}][\text{H}^+]^2 \quad (9)$$

where, $k = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{k_{-1} + k_2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}$

An explanation of the observed solvent isotope effect can be given from Scheme 1. It may be noted that the protonation step (i) is followed by the rate limiting hydrolysis step (ii), where the normal kinetic isotopic effect $k'_H/k'_D > 1$, while the solvent isotopic effect k'_{H_2O}/k'_{D_2O} is predicted to be < 1 for pre-equilibrium proton transfer followed

by the slow step. Thus, the observed isotope effect is composite of solvent isotope effect and the primary isotope effect of step (ii).

Thus assuming H_2OBr^+ as the reactive species, reaction Scheme 2 can be proposed in which the substrate is attacked at the nucleophilic sulphur site by the oxidant to form a sulphurane intermediate. The latter is attacked by the dipolar solvent. Elimination of H^+ and HBr results in the formation of methionine sulphoxide, which is oxidised by the second molecule of the oxidant. The four-electron stoichiometry shown for the reaction clearly rules out the formation of a sulphimide as a minor product which was noticed by Ruff and Kuczman¹⁸ during the oxidation of sulphides by CAB.

Scheme 3 explains the results obtained in the presence of halide (X^-) ion. The tight ion-pair formed in step (i) produces the inter-halogen compound ClBr or Br_2 which would oxidise the substrate in a fast step.

Scheme 3

Scheme 3 leads to rate law (10) in the form,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_6 K_4 [\text{BAB}][\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{X}^-]}{1 + K_4 [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{X}^-]} \quad (10)$$

which at constant $[H^+]$ reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_5 K_4 [\text{BAB}][X^-]}{1 + K_4 [X^-]} \quad (11)$$

Equation (10) is transformed into equation (12) for a double reciprocal plot of $k' \nu_s [Cl^-]$ in the form at constant $[H^+]$,

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{k_5 K_4 [H^+]^2 [Cl^-]} + \frac{1}{k_5} \quad (12)$$

From the straight line obtained ($r=0.9940$), k_5 and K_4 are $42.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $1460 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mol}^{-2}$ in presence of HCl, at $[H^+] = 0.07 \text{ M}$. These values are comparable with those obtained during the oxidation of dimethylsulphoxide^{2,3} with BAB ($k_5 = 41.27 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $K_4 = 1100 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mol}^{-2}$), thus establishing the values of the formation constant and decomposition constant of the species, $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Br} \dots \text{Cl}^-$.

Mechanism in alkaline medium: Oxidation of Mt by BAB in alkaline medium shows a first order dependence on the [oxidant] and a fractional order retardation with respect to the product of oxidation, benzenesulphonamide (ArSO_2NH_2). Further, the rate is independent of substrate concentration. Scheme 4 is able to explain the observed results.

Scheme 4

There is ample evidence¹⁶ to indicate the participation of hypobromous acid in reactions involving alkaline BAB solutions. From Scheme 4, assuming

steady state conditions for $[\text{NaOBr}]$ and with the approximation $[\text{RNH}^-] \approx [\text{RNH}_2]$, rate law (13) can be derived in agreement with experimental results.

$$-\frac{d[\text{BAB}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{BAB}][\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-1} [\text{RNH}_2] + k_2} \quad (13)$$

It is interesting to note that contrary to expectations, the rate of reaction has not increased in D_2O medium though OD^- is a stronger base than OH^- ion. The near equivalence of rates in the two media indicates that any increase in reaction rate is offset by the rate limiting hydrolysis, for which $k'_H/k'_D > 1$ is expected. Mechanism of oxidation of Mt by BAB in alkaline medium is similar to that of Scheme 2, except that the active species involved is HOBr.

References

1. M. S. AHMED and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Talanta*, 1980, **27**, 669.
2. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, S. ANANDA, A. S. A. MURTHY and K. S. RANGAPPA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 17.
3. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, S. ANANDA, A. S. A. MURTHY and K. S. RANGAPPA, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, **40**, 1673.
4. A. KUMAR, A. K. BOSE and S. P. MUSHRAN, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1926, **20**, 524, 1936, **30**, 1661.
5. N. C. WRIGHT, *Biochem. J.*, 1926, **20**, 524, 1936, **30**, 1661.
6. K. H. GENSCH and T. HIGUCHI, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1967, **56**, 177.
7. A. P. DELIYANNIS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, **56**, 13188.
8. F. JANCIK, F. BUBEN and J. KORBEL, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, **51**, 8369.
9. P. SPACU and H. DUMITRESU, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **79**, 62459.
10. C. F. DENT, *Biochem. J.*, 1947, **41**, 240.
11. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and N. M. M. GOWDA, *Talanta*, 1977, **24**, 270, *Macrochem. J.*, 1983, **28**, 235.
12. P. R. YOUNG and H. HSIEH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1978, **100**, 7121.
13. F. RUFF and A. KUCSMAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1982, 1075.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Organic Analysis", Longmans & Green, London, 1958, p. 503.
15. E. BISHOP and V. J. JENNINGS, *Talanta* 1958, **1**, 197.
16. F. F. HARDY and J. P. JOHNSTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1973, 742.
17. S. S. NARAYANAN and V. R. S. RAO, *Radiochem. Radioanal. Lett.*, 1981, **49**, 193.